

1 **Title**

2 **A Horizon scan for Arctic coastal biodiversity: understanding changes requires**
3 **international collaboration**

4
5 **Authors:**

6 Jakob Thyrring^{1,*}, Philippe Archambault², Michael Burrows³, Katrin Iken⁴, Fernando P.
7 Lima⁵, Joana Micael⁶, Markus Molis⁷, Catia Monteiro⁵, Sergej Olenin⁸, Paul E. Renaud⁹,
8 Ricardo A. Scrosati¹⁰, Rui Seabra⁵, Alexey A. Sukhotin¹¹, Jan Marcin Węśławski¹², Nadescha
9 Zwerschke¹³, Mikael K. Sejr¹

10
11 ¹ Aarhus University, Denmark (ORCID: JT: 0000-0002-1029-3105 / MSE: 0000-0001-8370-5791)

12 ² Takuvik, ArcticNet, Québec Océan, Université Laval Canada (ORCID: PA: 0000-0001-5986-6149)

13 ³ Scottish Association for Marine Science, United Kingdom (ORCID: MB: 0000-0003-4620-5899)

14 ⁵ University of Alaska Fairbanks, USA (ORCID: KI: 0000-0001-7961-1012)

15 ⁵ CIBIO, InBIO LA, BIOPOLIS, Universidade do Porto, Portugal (ORCID: RSe: 0000-0002-0240-
16 3992 / FL: 0000-0001-9575-9834 / CM: 0000-0002-5392-072X)

17 ⁶ Southwest Iceland Nature Research Centre, Iceland (ORCID: JM: 0000-0003-4658-5692)

18 ⁷ UiT - The Arctic University of Norway, Norway (ORCID: 0000-0002-0194-5984)

19 ⁸ Klaipėda University, Lithuania (ORCID: SO: 0000-0002-0773-1442)

20 ⁹ Akvaplan-niva, Norway (ORCID: PR: 0000-0003-3821-5974)

21 ¹⁰ St. Francis Xavier University, Canada (ORCID: RAS: 0000-0002-3050-132X)

22 ¹¹ Zoological Institute of RAS, Russia (ORCID: AAS: 0000-0003-2626-5317)

23 ¹² Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland (ORCID: JMW: 0000-0001 8434-
24 5927)

25 ¹³ Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, Greenland (ORCID: NZ: 0000-0003-4099-8269)

26
27
28
29 *Corresponding author: thyrring@ecos.au.dk

30
31 **Keywords:** Arctic shorelines, Benthos, Environmental change, Horizon scan, Multiple
32 stressors, Road map

42

43 **Abstract:**

44 Arctic coastal biodiversity faces increasing threats from anthropogenic activities and climate
45 change. However, the effects on biodiversity are still poorly understood, hindering actions
46 aimed at mitigating the impacts at a pan-Arctic scale. We present the results of a horizon scan
47 that provides a road map to address knowledge gaps on the influence of
48 anthropogenic activities, from increased shipping and harvesting to consequences of climate
49 change including increasing temperatures, cryosphere loss, and freshwater runoff. Predictions
50 on ecological change, species range expansions, and anthropogenic impacts on Arctic
51 coasts are hampered by the lack of biodiversity data and scarcity of biological long-term
52 monitoring programs. Filling these knowledge gaps will require coordinated international
53 efforts and standardized experiments across the diverse ecosystems characterizing the Arctic.

54

55 **Main text:**

56 *The Arctic coastline*

57 Based on the definition of the Arctic region given by the Conservation of Arctic Flora and
58 Fauna (Fig. 1), one fifth of Earth's coastlines are in the Arctic [1]. The Arctic coastal zone
59 encompasses a wide variety of habitats, including rocky shores, sedimentary beaches, kelp
60 beds, shallow lagoons, and river deltas (Fig. 2). These Arctic coastal systems are influenced by
61 a strong exchange of energy and matter with terrestrial and open-ocean ecosystems and the
62 cryosphere [2]. Healthy coastal ecosystems are of great importance to the millions of Arctic
63 inhabitants [3] who depend on them for subsistence food sources and other ecosystem services
64 underpinning their cultures and identities.

65 *Understanding threats to coastal biodiversity in a changing Arctic*

66 Arctic coastal ecosystems are experiencing pronounced environmental changes, with air
67 temperatures increasing three to seven times faster than the global average [4]. Biodiversity is
68 considered to facilitate many ecosystem services and resilience to change, but Arctic
69 biodiversity faces a growing number of anthropogenic pressures, including fishing, mining,
70 pollution, and the multi-faceted impacts of climate change. Recent warming has increased
71 melting of glaciers and sea ice, freshwater runoff, and permafrost thaw, which, together with
72 increased storminess, has accelerated coastal erosion [5]. Rivers export large quantities of
73 sediments, organic material, nutrients, and contaminants such as mercury to coastal habitats,
74 and the magnitudes and rates of physico-chemical changes observed along Arctic coasts [6],
75 which affect coastal species and their interactions at complex spatiotemporal scales, raise
76 concerns about biodiversity responses and ecosystem functioning. Yet, knowledge of how
77 these different stressors will affect patterns and drivers of Arctic coastal biodiversity is
78 extremely limited.

79 So far, Arctic coastal areas (defined here as having water depths less than 20 m) have been
80 poorly studied because access is difficult and the large icebreakers commonly used for Arctic
81 research cannot access shallow waters [7]. Additionally, only a few research stations that
82 include coastal biodiversity monitoring (<https://www.interact-gis.org>) exist across the Arctic.
83 Furthermore, the necessary logistic and safety measures make Arctic research costly and
84 impractical for many institutions. At this time, we are also struggling to predict the response of
85 coastal Arctic biodiversity to emerging stressors because prevailing ecological concepts
86 regarding the regulatory processes of species assemblages are largely based on research done
87 in non-polar environments [8-10] and are virtually untested in the Arctic. Current knowledge
88 on the influences of climate change on coastal Arctic species diversity and ecosystem structure
89 and function rests on studies done at a limited number of sites (i.e., specific shorelines or fjords)
90 [e.g. 11-15]. Although those studies provide essential information on local ecology, our

91 capacity to detect commonalities across the diversity of Arctic coastal landscapes remains very
92 limited, and the lack of knowledge on ecological interactions such as predation, competition,
93 and facilitation in Arctic coastal communities seriously hampers our ability to predict
94 biodiversity responses to climate change and increased human activities.

95 Here, we present the results of a horizon scan conducted at a meeting in Copenhagen, Denmark,
96 in January 2024 aimed at identifying issues of concern for coastal biodiversity across the Arctic
97 region. We followed a well-established horizon scan protocol [16] (see Box 1 for methods). We
98 present these issues in no particular order and conclude with a road map on how to address
99 important knowledge gaps across the Arctic region.

100

101 **Horizon scan results**

102 *Lack of benchmark knowledge*

103 Assessing change in coastal biological communities requires biodiversity knowledge obtained
104 through standardized sampling, but few comprehensive pan-Arctic coastal biodiversity datasets
105 exist. The available species records are taxonomically incomplete and spatially and temporally
106 biased towards easily accessible seasons and sites. The resulting partial picture of native species
107 composition defines a key challenge for assessing future changes in biodiversity. Some of the
108 available long-term monitoring programs of Arctic coastal biodiversity, such as in the White
109 Sea [15,17], Svalbard [13,18], and Alaska [19,20] have demonstrated profound recent changes
110 in Arctic ecosystems, but monitoring a few sites will not provide a large-scale understanding of
111 how changing conditions might impact Arctic coastal biodiversity as physico-chemical
112 conditions vary across regions and fjords. Reduced data availability may also result from a
113 culture of not sharing data from monitoring programs or research projects. Hence, data sharing,
114 greater spatiotemporal coverage, and integration of biodiversity data across all Arctic nations
115 constitute an urgent need [21].

116

117 *Changing cryosphere and intensified land-ocean coupling*

118 Disappearing sea ice threatens to species associated with coastal sea ice ecosystems (from ice
119 algae to polar bears, *Ursus maritimus*), while potentially benefitting other species as conditions
120 change and new habitats become available [22,23]. For example, warming and a prolonged
121 open-water period could facilitate the expansion of foundation species such as mussels,
122 macroalgae, and seagrasses [24,25], enhancing coastal biodiversity [26,27]. However, the
123 increasing runoff from melting glaciers and thawing permafrost locally decreases coastal water
124 clarity due to increased suspended sediments, counterbalancing the effect of a longer ice-free
125 period by reducing the amount of light reaching different depths of the water column, a process
126 termed coastal darkening [28]. Coastal darkening may decrease primary production by
127 macroalgae, seagrasses, and phytoplankton and, thus, reduce the abundance of foundation
128 species that either depend on phytoplankton for food (e.g. filter-feeders) or light as energy
129 source (macroalgae and seagrasses).

130

131 *Non-indigenous species, parasites, and the emergence of pathogens*

132 Arctic sea ice is becoming thinner and the seasonal sea ice freezes later and melts earlier. Less
133 ice increases ship traffic through the Northwest Passage and the Northern Sea Route ('Northeast
134 Passage'). Together with ocean warming, increased shipping might increase the risk of range
135 expansions of non-indigenous species to the Arctic from the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans,
136 potentially altering species interactions. Recently, species distribution modelling has predicted
137 that Hudson Bay, Labrador, the Chukchi/Eastern Bering Seas, and the Barents/White Seas are
138 particularly vulnerable to future intrusions of non-indigenous species [22,29]. The rate of
139 change may depend on physical barriers, such as island chains, and on the exposure to influx
140 of Atlantic or Pacific waters [30]. North-flowing currents influence some Arctic areas such as
141 Svalbard or the Chukchi Sea, facilitating range extensions of species from lower latitudes, in

142 contrast to a greater isolation of other areas such as the Russian Severnaya Zemlya Archipelago
143 [31].

144 Invasive species may change coastal biodiversity and ecosystem functioning [32] through
145 changes in food web structure. In the 1960's, the non-indigenous red king crab *Paralithodes*
146 *camtschaticus* was introduced to the Barents Sea to create a new commercial fishery. Today,
147 the king crab is considered invasive in this region, where it has decreased biodiversity at depths
148 > 100 m in Arctic Norway [33]. However, only a few studies have investigated experimentally
149 the importance of biotic interactions in shaping Arctic coastal communities [14,34]. Therefore,
150 limitations in current knowledge preclude predictions about the impacts of non-indigenous
151 species and novel biotic interactions on coastal biodiversity [35].

152 Warming can also facilitate the range expansion of pathogens such as invertebrate parasites,
153 fungi, bacteria, and viruses, which may alter species composition through species-specific
154 effects. Such pathogens can cause widespread host mortality and population collapse such as
155 those documented from lower-latitude coastal systems [36,37]. Transmissible cancer has
156 previously been reported for a range of bivalve species in Europe and North America [38] and,
157 recently, transmissible cancer cell lineages were detected in blue mussels (*Mytilus* spp.) from
158 the Barents Sea [39]. However, the ecological impacts, and associated risks to subsistence
159 communities, of such pathogens on their hosts and Arctic coastal biodiversity in general remain
160 largely unknown.

161

162 *Biodiversity and the blue economy*

163 Climate change is making the Arctic region more navigable, and the ever-rising human need
164 of food, energy, and minerals means that industry is following the retreating ice northward.
165 Rapid growth of the blue economy in the Arctic has led to projected Arctic investments of more
166 than US\$ 1 trillion over the coming decades [3]. Harvesting of living marine resources will
167 inevitably alter biodiversity and habitat integrity. Increased aquaculture activities risks

168 changing local nutrient balance, with direct effects on (harmful) algal blooms and indirect
169 effects through impacts on dissolved oxygen concentration, water clarity, sediment organic
170 enrichment, and heavy-metal concentration. All ship-based activities and oil production itself
171 come with the threat of pollution from oil spills as well as providing vectors for the introduction
172 of non-indigenous species. Man-made structures, such as oil rigs and renewable energy
173 platforms, are stepping stones for subsequent dispersal and range expansions of northward-
174 moving species [40,41]. Given that most hydrocarbon production projects in the Arctic take
175 place in coastal regions and/or have associated coastal infrastructure (e.g.
176 shipment/transshipment terminals), coastal regions are particularly at risk. As we note
177 elsewhere, each of these human impacts can alter the biodiversity of native biological
178 communities through mortality or alterations in food web dynamics, so efforts must ensure that
179 economic development in the Arctic is ecologically sustainable and includes monitoring and
180 spill-response programs.

181

182 *Impacts of multiple stressors*

183 Workshop participants flagged the importance of understanding how interacting abiotic and
184 biotic drivers affect species distribution and community structure, as these drivers can exert
185 synergistic or antagonistic effects that make it impossible to predict the direction and
186 magnitude of effects without empirical support. For example, exposure to low pH can
187 exacerbate thermal stress effects by increasing the susceptibility of intertidal benthic
188 invertebrates to freezing (synergistic effect) [42]. In addition, when multiple stressors create
189 synergistic effects, they can generate earlier tipping points (zones of rapid change in a nonlinear
190 relationship between a response variable and the intensity of a stressor) in aquatic ecosystems
191 [43]. Yet, very few studies have assessed the combined effects of multiple stressors on coastal
192 Arctic species [e.g. 44-46], rendering the Arctic severely understudied in this regard.
193 Furthermore, genetic diversity in natural populations enhances the resistance and adaptive

194 potential when facing multiple stressors, and adaptation can enhance their resilience to stress
195 on an evolutionary scale [47]. Thus, understanding the responses of biodiversity to
196 environmental change requires knowledge on the sensitivity to multiple stressors across
197 various levels of biological organization, especially considering that even a moderate increase
198 in environmental stress can alter community structure [48].

199

200 *Concluding Remarks: A roadmap for safeguarding future biodiversity*

201 The scarcity of international and interdisciplinary collaboration represents one of the most
202 important barriers to understand anthropogenic impacts at greater spatial scales, pointing to the
203 need to synthesize knowledge and coordinate observational and experimental approaches.
204 Furthermore, the current lack of baseline biodiversity data and experimental tests of ecological
205 theory in the coastal Arctic limits our ability to understand community assembly processes in
206 this system (see Outstanding Questions). Increased international collaboration and coordinated
207 pan-Arctic monitoring would help to create a benchmark inventory to better understand
208 ongoing and future changes in Arctic coastal biodiversity, identifying mechanistic links related
209 to climate change and other anthropogenic pressures.

210 The comparison of ecological responses to changing external drivers across regions throughout
211 the Arctic based on monitoring and standardized experiments on different coasts is needed to
212 reveal commonalities in the mechanisms affecting community assembly across the
213 heterogeneous Arctic region (Box 2). Understanding the challenges facing biodiversity requires
214 expanded sampling efforts across Arctic coastal systems ideally spanning different seasons,
215 enabling predictions for geographic areas with the greatest sensitivity to change. Monitoring
216 efforts would benefit from supplementing academic science efforts with indigenous and local
217 knowledge as well as citizen science [49]. The establishment of additional coastal marine
218 protected areas, particularly in areas of high biodiversity, could help to preserve extant
219 biodiversity from increasing human activities. Beyond the threats that human activities impose

220 through pollution, eutrophication, and habitat alteration, human activities also increase the risk
221 of introducing invasive species, and these risks require mitigation. We acknowledge that the
222 global nature of climate change threats to biodiversity is not limited to the Arctic. However,
223 few other systems are so severely understudied while at the forefront of climate change. A
224 wider spatial coverage of Arctic biodiversity will improve efforts to understand global
225 biodiversity patterns, drivers and improve predictions on which species will thrive or decline,
226 refine management efforts, and ultimately help us more effectively to forecast the future of
227 Arctic coastal biodiversity.

228

229 **Declaration of interests**

230 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

231

232 **Acknowledgements:**

233 The authors would like to thank the Carlsberg Foundation (grant ID: CF23-0321) for
234 supporting the horizon scan workshop. This paper is a contribution from the Arctic Coastal
235 Biodiversity Observation Network (ARC-BON) and the Horizon Europe project POMP (Polar
236 Ocean Mitigation Potential; grant ID: 101136875). JT was supported by the Carlsberg
237 Foundation (grant ID: CF21-0564) and the Independent Research Fund Denmark (grant ID:
238 10.46540/3120-00045B). CM, FPL, and RS were supported by OceanLog (grant ID:
239 PTDC/BIA-BMA/4848/2021), ANERIS (grant ID: 101094924) and FLAD. PR received
240 support from the FRAM center project Catchment to Coast. AS was supported by the
241 Zoological Institute of RAS Assignment # 125012800889-2. SO was partly supported by the
242 Research Council of Lithuania EIDEMBUKTA (grant ID: S-MIP-22-48). RAS was supported
243 by the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC Discovery
244 Grant, grant ID: 311624). KI was supported by the NSF-funded Beaufort Lagoon Ecosystem
245 LTER (grant ID: 2322664) and by the U.S. Marine Biodiversity Observation Network

Preprint version – published version available her:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0169534725000369>

246 (MBON) co-organized by NOAA, NASA, BOEM, and ONR through the National
247 Oceanographic Partnership Program (NOPP) (grant IDs: NOAA NA19NOS0120198; NASA
248 80NSSC22K1780; ONR N00014-22-1-2792).

249

250 **Figures:**

251 **Figure 1: The Arctic region.** No single definition exists for the Arctic region. Given our focus
252 on biodiversity in this article, we follow the definition of Conservation of Arctic Flora and
253 Fauna (CAFF) group (orange line). Modified with permission from GRID-Arendal
254 (<https://www.grida.no/resources/8387>).

255

256

257

258 **Figure 2: The diversity of Arctic coastal environments. A.** Rocky intertidal shore dominated
259 by macroalgae during summer near Nuuk, West Greenland (Photo: Jakob Thyrring). **B.** Rocky
260 intertidal shore incrustated in ice (known as the ice foot) during winter near Qaanaaq, West
261 Greenland (Photo: Jakob Thyrring). The ice foot protects intertidal organisms from extremely
262 low air temperatures. **C.** Sea ice breaking up in the Gulf of St. Lawrence coast of Nova Scotia,
263 Canada. The sea ice break-up exposes the surface water to sunlight, stimulating primary
264 production. Still, it also increases disturbance to the seafloor and intertidal habitats as drifting
265 ice scours substrates (Photo: Ricardo Scrosati). **D.** Plume of sediment exported from a land-
266 terminating glacier in Young Sound, East Greenland. The plume decreases light availability in
267 the water column and decreases primary productivity (Photo: Mikael Sejr). **E.** Export of
268 sediments from land is increasing delta progradation and thus the extent of soft-bottom habitats
269 across the Arctic (Photo: Nikolaj Krog Larsen). **F.** Post-glacial lagoon near Eidembukta,
270 Svalbard. Post-glacial lagoons usually form in front of retreating glaciers, and the lagoon fills
271 with freshwater and seawater (Photo: Jakub (Kuba) Witek). **G.** Subtidal macroalgal meadow,
272 which commonly occur throughout many Arctic coastal waters (Photo: Peter Bondo). **H.**
273 Subtidal soft bottom community inhabited by brittle stars and buried infauna (Photo: Mikael K
274 Sejr). **I.** Hard bottom community dominated by encrusting algae and anemones (Photo: Peter
275 Bondo).

276

277

278

279 **Box 1: Horizon scanning methods**

280 The scanning process began in 2023, when experts on the ecology and ecophysiology of polar
281 coastal marine species were invited to a workshop in Copenhagen, Denmark, held in January
282 2024. Experts were selected to provide a wide expertise in ecology, physiology, genomics,
283 ecological modeling, and food web dynamics. All experts were asked to identify key questions
284 to advance knowledge on current threats to coastal Arctic biodiversity. Fourteen scientists from
285 10 countries attended the workshop. Participants were divided in groups to discuss and
286 prioritize their responses and vote on their priorities. The list of priorities was compiled and
287 discussed in plenum. Through a final round of voting, all participants agreed on a final list. The
288 inputs from the invited Russian colleague was provided through virtual meetings before and
289 after the workshop.

290

291

292 **Box 2: Pan-Arctic standardized long-term monitoring**

293 Researchers are recognizing the importance of coordinated standardized long-term biodiversity
294 monitoring to detect the impacts of human activities and climate change. The patchy
295 distribution of current marine Arctic monitoring programs and differences in methodologies
296 and sampling efforts limit efforts to synthesize these initiatives to gain a more holistic
297 understanding of the effects on Arctic coastal biodiversity. The Arctic Council, an
298 intergovernmental forum promoting cooperation among Arctic nations, has established the
299 Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Programme (CBMP), which is currently developing an
300 *Arctic Coastal Biodiversity Monitoring Plan* based on science and indigenous knowledge [50].
301 Although ecosystem-wide monitoring provides pivotal knowledge, the required efforts and
302 associated costs limit their geographical scope to a few sites, often located close to cities or
303 research stations. Thus, integrating low-cost, low-maintenance monitoring tools into ongoing
304 monitoring efforts would enable researchers to track changes in biodiversity across the Arctic
305 over the coming decades. For example, the relatively easy access to rocky intertidal habitats
306 during low tides (when free of ice) together with the monitoring of permanent plots may be
307 particularly amenable to frequently assess changes in community structure and the abundance
308 of ecologically important species. Subtidal biodiversity can likewise be monitored using
309 permanent plots visited by scuba divers or photographed using ROVs or drop cameras.
310 Decreasing costs and rapid improvements in sequencing techniques makes environmental DNA
311 (eDNA) an easy-to-standardize and non-invasive approach suitable for large-scale monitoring
312 in intertidal and subtidal habitats. However, while eDNA efficiently detects rare and newly
313 established species, the lack of barcodes for Arctic species represents significant gaps for DNA
314 databases and restrict the use of eDNA to supplement visual biodiversity monitoring on a pan-
315 Arctic scale. Finally, remote sensing can track biophysical changes at local to regional scales
316 and, in combination, provide a large-scale perspective on Arctic biodiversity.

317

318 **References:**

- 319 1. CAFF (2013) *Arctic biodiversity assessment - status and trends in Arctic biodiversity*,
320 Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna, Akureyri.
321
- 322 2. Sejr, M.K. *et al.* (2024) Multiple climatic drivers increase pace and consequences of
323 ecosystem change in the Arctic Coastal Ocean. *Limnol Oceanogr Lett* 9, 683-695.
324
- 325 3. Atkisson, A. *et al.* (2018) *Getting it right in a new ocean: Bringing Sustainable Blue*
326 *Economy Principles to the Arctic*, <http://arcticwwf/ocean>.
327
- 328 4. Rantanen, M. *et al.* (2022) The Arctic has warmed nearly four times faster than the
329 globe since 1979. *Commun Earth Environ* 3, 168.
330
- 331 5. Overeem, I. *et al.* (2011) Sea ice loss enhances wave action at the Arctic coast.
332 *Geophys Res Lett* 38, L17503.
333
- 334 6. Hernes, P.J. *et al.* (2021) Element cycling and aquatic function in a changing Arctic.
335 *Limnol Oceanogr* 66, S1-S16.
336
- 337 7. Fritz, M. *et al.* (2017) Collapsing Arctic coastlines. *Nat Clim Chang* 7, 6-7.
338
- 339 8. Bruno, J.F. *et al.* (2003) Inclusion of facilitation into ecological theory. *Trends Ecol*
340 *Evol* 18, 119-125.
341
- 342 9. Silliman, B.R. and He, Q. (2018) Physical stress, consumer control, and new theory in
343 ecology. *Trends Ecol Evol* 33, 492-503.
344
- 345 10. Menge, B.A. and Sutherland, J.P. (1987) Community Regulation: Variation in
346 Disturbance, Competition, and Predation in Relation to Environmental Stress and
347 Recruitment. *Am Nat* 130, 730-757.
348
- 349 11. Sejr, M.K. *et al.* (2021) Small scale factors modify impacts of temperature, ice scour
350 and waves and drive rocky intertidal community structure in a Greenland fjord. *Front*
351 *Mar Sci* 7, 607135
352
- 353 12. Sejr, M.K. *et al.* (2022) Glacial meltwater determines the balance between autotrophic
354 and heterotrophic processes in a Greenland fjord. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 119,
355 e2207024119.
356
- 357 13. Węśławski, J.M. *et al.* (2010) Increase in biodiversity in the arctic rocky littoral,
358 Sorkapland, Svalbard, after 20 years of climate warming. *Mar Biodivers* 40, 123-
359 130.
360
- 361 14. Díaz, M.J. *et al.* (2023) Limited predatory effects on infaunal macrobenthos
362 community patterns in intertidal soft-bottom of Arctic coasts. *Ecol Evol* 13, e9779.
363
- 364 15. Naumov, A.D. (2013) Long-term fluctuations of soft-bottom intertidal community
365 structure affected by ice cover at two small sea bights in the Chupa Inlet
366 (Kandalaksha Bay) of the White Sea. *Hydrobiologia* 706, 159-173.
367

- 368 16. Sutherland, W.J. *et al.* (2024) A horizon scan of global biological conservation issues
369 for 2024. *Trends Ecol Evol* 39, 89-100.
370
- 371 17. Azovsky, A.I. *et al.* (2023) Long-term dynamics of subarctic intertidal macrofauna:
372 common trends and the role of local environment. *Estuaries Coasts* 46, 740-756.
373
- 374 18. Al-Habahbeh, A.K. *et al.* (2020) Arctic coastal benthos long-term responses to
375 perturbations under climate warming. *Philos Trans A Math Phys Eng Sci* 378,
376 20190355.
377
- 378 19. Danielson, S. *et al.* (2022) Monitoring Alaskan Arctic shelf ecosystems with an
379 informal observation network. *Oceanography* 35, 198-209.
380
- 381 20. Bonsell, C. and Dunton, K.H. (2018) Long-term patterns of benthic irradiance and
382 kelp production in the central Beaufort sea reveal implications of warming for Arctic
383 inner shelves. *Prog Oceanogr* 162, 160-170.
384
- 385 21. Thyrring, J. *et al.* (2024) Shallow coverage in shallow waters: the incompleteness of
386 intertidal species inventories in biodiversity database records. *Ecography* 2024,
387 e07006.
388
- 389 22. Goldsmit, J. *et al.* (2020) What and where? Predicting invasion hotspots in the Arctic
390 marine realm. *Glob Chang Biol* 26, 4752-4771.
391
- 392 23. Pavlova, L.V. *et al.* (2023) The impact of sea ice loss on benthic communities of the
393 Makarov Strait (Northeastern Barents Sea). *Animals* 13, 2320.
394
- 395 24. Thyrring, J. *et al.* (2017) Rising air temperatures will increase intertidal mussel
396 abundance in the Arctic. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 584, 91-104.
397
- 398 25. Assis, J. *et al.* (2022) Major expansion of marine forests in a warmer arctic. *Front*
399 *Mar Sci* 9, 850368.
400
- 401 26. Lavoie, C. *et al.* (2024) Living under Arctic kelp forests: Linking soft-bottom
402 communities to kelp cover in the Canadian Arctic. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 740, 1-22
403
- 404 27. Cameron, N.M. *et al.* (2024) Global taxonomic and functional patterns in invertebrate
405 assemblages from rocky-intertidal mussel beds. *Sci Rep* 14, 26.
406
- 407 28. Attard, K. *et al.* (2024) Seafloor primary production in a changing Arctic Ocean. *Proc*
408 *Natl Acad Sci* 121, e2303366121.
409
- 410 29. Goldsmit, J. *et al.* (2018) Projecting present and future habitat suitability of ship-
411 mediated aquatic invasive species in the Canadian Arctic. *Biol Invasions* 20, 501-517.
412
- 413 30. Krumhansl, K. *et al.* (2023) Permeability of coastal biogeographic barriers to marine
414 larval dispersal on the east and west coasts of North America. *Glob Ecol Biogeo* 32,
415 945-961.
416

- 417 31. Sirenko, B.I., ed (2001) *List of species of free-living invertebrates of Eurasian Arctic*
418 *seas and adjacent deep waters*. Explorations of the Fauna and the Seas, 51, Russian
419 Academy of Sciences, Zoological Institute.
- 420 32. Cottier-Cook, E.J. *et al.* (2024) Horizon scanning of potential threats to high-Arctic
421 biodiversity, human health and the economy from marine invasive alien species: A
422 Svalbard case study. *Glob Change Biol* 30, e17009.
- 423
- 424 33. Oug, E. *et al.* (2011) Effects of the invasive red king crab (*Paralithodes*
425 *camtschaticus*) on soft-bottom fauna in Varangerfjorden, northern Norway. *Mar*
426 *Biodivers* 41, 467-479.
- 427
- 428 34. Khalaman, V.V. *et al.* (2016) Algae versus animals in early fouling communities of the
429 White Sea. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 553, 13-32
- 430
- 431 35. Goldsmit, J. *et al.* (2024) Predicted shifts in suitable habitat of interacting benthic
432 species in a warmer and invaded Canadian Arctic. *Elementa* 12, 1, 00018.
- 433
- 434 36. Mouritsen, K.N. *et al.* (2005) Climate warming may cause a parasite-induced collapse
435 in coastal amphipod populations. *Oecologia* 146, 476-483.
- 436
- 437 37. Hewson, I. *et al.* (2023) A scuticociliate causes mass mortality of *Diadema antillarum*
438 in the Caribbean Sea. *Sci Adv* 9, eadg3200.
- 439
- 440 38. Barber, B.J. (2004) Neoplastic diseases of commercially important marine bivalves.
441 *Aquat Living Resour* 17, 449-466
- 442
- 443 39. Skazina, M. *et al.* (2023) Genetic features of bivalve transmissible neoplasia in blue
444 mussels from the Kola Bay (Barents Sea) suggest a recent trans-Arctic migration of
445 the cancer lineages. *Mol Ecol* 32, 5724-5741.
- 446
- 447 40. Mayorga-Adame, C.G. *et al.* (2022) Spatiotemporal scales of larval dispersal and
448 connectivity among oil and gas structures in the North Sea. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 685,
449 49-67
- 450
- 451 41. Adams, T.P. *et al.* (2014) Offshore marine renewable energy devices as stepping
452 stones across biogeographical boundaries. *J Appl Ecol* 51, 330-338.
- 453
- 454 42. Thyrring, J. *et al.* (2023) Ocean acidification increases susceptibility to sub-zero air
455 temperatures in ecosystem engineers and limits poleward range shifts. *eLife* 12,
456 e81080.
- 457
- 458 43. Carrier-Belleau, C. *et al.* (2023) Tipping point arises earlier under a multiple-stressor
459 scenario. *Sci Rep* 13, 16780.
- 460
- 461 44. Beaudreau, N. *et al.* (2024) Using a metabolomics approach to investigate the
462 sensitivity of a potential Arctic-invader and its Arctic sister-species to marine
463 heatwaves and traditional harvesting disturbances. *Sci Total Environ* 917, 170167.
- 464
- 465 45. Nielsen, M.B. *et al.* (2021) Freshening increases the susceptibility to heat stress in
466 intertidal mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) from the Arctic. *J Ani Ecol* 90, 1515-1524.
- 467

- 468 46. Diehl, N. *et al.* (2020) Impacts of combined temperature and salinity stress on the
469 endemic Arctic brown seaweed *Laminaria solidungula* J. Agardh. *Polar Biol* 43, 647-
470 656.
- 471 47. Meester, L. *et al.* (2018) Genetic adaptation as a biological buffer against climate
472 change: Potential and limitations. *Integr Zool* 13, 372-391.
- 473
- 474 48. Heaven, C.S. and Scrosati, R.A. (2008) Benthic community composition across
475 gradients of intertidal elevation, wave exposure, and ice scour in Atlantic Canada.
476 *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 369, 13-23
- 477
- 478 49. Eicken, H. *et al.* (2021) Connecting top-down and bottom-up approaches in
479 environmental observing. *BioScience* 71, 467-483.
- 480
- 481 50. CAFF (2019) *Arctic Coastal Biodiversity Monitoring Plan*. Conservation of Arctic
482 Flora and Fauna International Secretariat: Akureyri, Iceland.